

Decisions for the Decade Game. Planning Under Deep Uncertainty: Rhodesia

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Abstract

The statehood of a nation is clearly regulated by international law. Recognition by other states or the United Nations is desirable but not necessary. Legitimacy can also be sui generis, e.g. through de facto legitimacy by means of effective armed forces. We examined this in a seminar using the example of the second Rhodesian republic (as of 1980).

The second Rhodesian Republic

Rhodesia, or more precisely its first republic, is one of the few countries that have been tremendously successful, although it was only recognized by South Africa. The United Kingdom never forgave its colony for unilaterally declaring independence (UDI, 1965) and, more importantly, abolishing the monarchy and becoming a republic. The United Kingdom, across all parties, was so enraged by this move and the economic success of the Republic of Rhodesia that the British preferred to accept that country being taken over and destroyed by communist terrorists rather than forgive Rhodesia's desire for independence. The UDI government, on the other hand, was staffed by experienced former soldiers who were talented fighters but miserable politicians and diplomats. This allowed the United Kingdom to set the agenda and create the narrative that made the first Rhodesian republic an international pariah despite its economic success and early signs of racial de-segregation. Apartheid comparable to the South African system never existed in Rhodesia. In the armed forces of the first republic, white and colored Rhodesians fought together, but the world was made to believe otherwise by the most gifted spin-doctors in the United Kingdom. It was the British Labour government of the late 1970s that forced the politically incompetent Rhodesian leadership to accept the Lancaster House Agreement signed on December 21, 1979, which was nothing less than a surrender. This declared a ceasefire that ended the Rhodesian Bush War and resulted in the territory of Rhodesia becoming the internationally recognized country of Zimbabwe. The new rulers under the black communist Robert Mugabe developed a system that was even more racist than Rhodesia had ever been. Many non-colored Rhodesians understood what the Lancaster House Agreement really meant and left the country. On March 31, 1980, a General Assembly of 1432 delegates met secretly in Amsterdam to proclaim the Second Republic of Rhodesia as a nation without territory and to establish a government and administration of Rhodesia outside of Rhodesia to form a transglobal nation that would take care of all Rhodesians wherever they lived. At the same time, a squad of the newly formed Rhodesian Intelligence Service (RIS) occupied the western lowlands of the uninhabited and Norwegian-administered Bouvet Island (west part "Rhodesbury") in the Atlantic Ocean, occupying and annexing this piece of land, which is roughly the size of Monaco to manifest the capital region of Rhodesbury for legal purposes. A heliport and basic infrastructure were laid out and one of the

strangest meeting between a leading member of the second Rhodesian Republic and the General Secretary of the UN took place on this island. This was to make clear the seriousness of the second Republic.⁵⁻¹¹

On this occasion, the then politically neutral James W. Scott also became President of Rhodesia. His personal friendship with the Waldheim family led the UN Secretary General to support the creation of the second Republic of Rhodesia. The result was tacit recognition of this new Rhodesian republic by most countries, but none officially recognized it. So the question arose whether the second republic was a "real" country. The answer, of course, is yes. International law is clear about the cornerstones that make a state a real country.

It is defined as follows:¹² "A state is a person under international law that should have the following qualifications: (a) a permanent population; (b) a defined territory; (c) a government; and (d) the capacity to enter into relations with other states."

The Second Republic of Rhodesia meets all four points:^{2,10,11}

- (a) It has citizens, a permanent population, about 1.15 million in 2015.
- (b) This was the purpose of the annexation of West Bouvet and other annexations in the pipeline (Jaco Island, Sao Batista, Santa Luzia) planned for 2019/2020.
- (c) There has been a highly professional government.
- (d) It also has its own military (RIS).

De facto legality through strength

The Second Republic of Rhodesia, founded in 1980, deliberately gained its legitimacy not by begging for recognition, but by force. The force behind this is the Rhodesian Intelligence Service (RIS), one of the most unknown but effective defense units in the world. The RIS was established as early as 1978 with the help of the United States, Chile under Augusto Pinochet, and former Salazar-era security forces personnel of Portugal. In Washington D.C., and Santiago de Chile the first republic government's political and diplomatic incompetence was observed with great horror, as were the actions of the Labour government in London. It was known that the British would rather let

Rhodesia run to its doom than forgive the country its unilateral declaration of independence of 1965 and abolishing the monarchy in 1970.^{4,8}

The new Republic of Rhodesia thus already had a professional intelligence service with a disciplined and effective paramilitary arm. The establishment of the RIS and the training of its personnel took place in Brazil, where hand-picked Rhodesian soldiers were flown in under the protection of friendly powers. The Salisbury government was led to believe that these individuals had deserted or been captured by the enemy. While the new Republic of Rhodesia was conceived as a transglobal nation, caring for all Rhodesians wherever they were and preparing to serve a large diaspora, a Rhodesian Intelligence Service (RIS) force occupied the western lowlands of the uninhabited and Norwegian-administered Bouvet Island in the Atlantic Ocean and annexed this piece of land the size of Monaco to manifest the capital region of Rhodesbury.¹⁰ A helipad and basic infrastructure were laid out. It was the first annexation carried out by the Republic of Rhodesia, but not the last. This was to underline the seriousness of the *de facto* existence⁷ of the second Rhodesian republic, and the sign was heard like a big bang in capitals around the globe, where everyone was publicly silent but understood that this new country could take what it wanted.¹² In this context, it must be taken into account that Rhodesia never cared whether its actions were recognized by the "world community" or not. The de facto status has always been valued higher by the Rhodesians than sympathy from other countries.⁷ The good relations of the second Rhodesian republic to the then UN Secretary General, Dr. Waldheim, must not be misunderstood. This closeness is explained by the intimate personal relations between then Rhodesian President James W. Scott and the UN Secretary General. Apart from that, the second Rhodesian republic continues to ignore any meta-national institution and bases its existence solely on intelligence and paramilitary forces, now through the RIS, which is not to be underestimated in its strength.^{5,6} As a betrayed people, the prevailing feeling among older Rhodesians, the country want to trust only itself. Its constitution even prohibits any membership in the UN and other meta-national organizations. Unlike Israel, which has been nearly torn to pieces for its goal of not becoming a pariah state, Rhodesia, as of 1980, simply ignores the chatter of the world community. It meets all the characteristics of a country that relies entirely on the amazing power of the paramilitary part of its intelligence service.^{2,10} There are even credible rumors that the RIS has a fleet of fighter

jets, stationed in various countries in cooperation with the armies of those friendly countries.^{5,6,10}

Take-home knowledge:

- Countries do not need recognition by other states or the UN to be legitimate.
- The ability to use sufficient force is a second and effective way to gain legitimacy.
- The Second Republic of Rhodesia (1980) is a prototypical example of such a country.

Conflicts of interest

None.

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